

Traveling wave method for event localization and characterization of power transmission lines

Marko Hudomalj^{a,b,*}, Andrej Trost^c, Andrej Čampa^{a,b}

^a Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

^b Consensus d.o.o, Dob, Slovenia

^c University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Ljubljana, Slovenia

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ABSTRACT

Traveling wave theory is deployed today to improve the monitoring of transmission lines in electrical power grids. Most traveling wave methods require prior knowledge of the wave propagation characteristic of the transmission line, which is a major source of error as the value changes during the operation of the line. To improve the localization of events on transmission lines, we propose a new online localization method that simultaneously determines the frequency-dependent wave propagation characteristic from the traveling wave measurements of the event. Compared to conventional methods, this is achieved with one additional traveling wave measurement, but the method can still be applied in different measurement setups. We have derived the method based on the complex continuous wavelet transform. The accuracy of the method is evaluated in a simulation with a frequency-dependent transmission line model of the IEEE 39-bus system. The method was developed independently of the type of event and evaluated in test setups considering different lengths of the monitored line, line types and event locations. The localization accuracy is compared with existing online methods and analyzed with regard to the characterization capabilities. The method has a high relative localization accuracy in the range of 0.1% under different test conditions.

1. Introduction

With the development of smart grids and the increasing complexity of electrical power systems, the need for advanced monitoring and decision making is becoming increasingly important. This is especially true for transmission lines, which are crucial for grid operation but are typically long and often inaccessible and therefore difficult to monitor. In addition to established monitoring systems for slowly changing electrical properties, many efforts have recently been made to develop new systems that detect and respond to fast dynamic events [1]. More recently, the introduction of phasor measurement units (PMUs) in distribution and their ability to provide accurate synchronized measurements has enabled the detection and localization of events [2]. Although PMUs are excellent for monitoring electrical variables in steady and quasi-steady state conditions [3], they are not capable of detecting fast transient events. Solutions based on traveling wave (TW) theory [4] are used to better detect, localize and react to fast transient events [1]. TW solutions for transmission lines are applied to different types of transient events: faults [5,6], lightning strikes [7,8] and partial discharges (PD) [9,10]. The developed methods are applied to a specific use case in combination with the type of event, but in this paper, we only focus on the event localization capabilities.

Transient events trigger TWs on transmission lines that propagate away from the source [11]. TWs are attenuated and dispersed due to the frequency-dependent electromagnetic wave propagation characteristic of the medium $\gamma(f)$ [4]. The attenuation reduces the wave amplitude and the dispersion elongates the wave in time. At the ends of the line sections where the medium changes, part of the wave is reflected and part is transmitted. Fig. 1 shows a schematic overview of TW propagation on a transmission line. The TWs are visualized with the lattice diagram, over which detailed waveforms are shown at the source and measurement locations. The TWs propagate in both directions and are reflected at the line ends.

TW methods on transmission lines can be differentiated according to the number of measurement devices required, methods for processing TWs and the consideration of wave propagation characteristic.

Based on the number of devices, there are three main types [5]: single-terminal [12,13], double-terminal [14,15] and multi-terminal [16,17]. The single-terminal methods require one measurement device at one end of the line, such as M_1 in Fig. 1. These methods are based on the detection of incident and reflected waves. Since only one device is required, no synchronization of devices is necessary. However, the detection of reflected waves requires high measurement resolution,

* Corresponding author at: Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia.

E-mail address: marko.hudomalj@ijs.si (M. Hudomalj).

Fig. 1. Lattice diagram of TW propagation on a transmission line with measurement devices. TW signals $s_i(t)$ are shown over the lattice diagram at the event location and the locations of measurement devices.

as the waves are attenuated by the reflection and the propagation times of the waves are longer compared to the incident waves [18]. Furthermore, it must be assumed that the reflection does not change the wave phase and one must address the potential problems with branched networks where reflected waves from different branches can precede each other and therefore cannot be distinguished. The double-terminal type requires two measurement devices, one at each end of the monitored line, in Fig. 1 represented by M_1 and M_3 . In this case, both devices detect the incident waves. On the one hand, the localization accuracy is improved, while on the other hand, there are high requirements for time synchronization of the devices [19]. Today, Global Positioning System (GPS) synchronization meets most of the requirements [15]. Multi-terminal methods work with multiple devices that are typically positioned at the ends of the line branches [20,21] or on a single line [22], as shown in Fig. 1. For most of these methods, it must be assumed that the medium does not change in the different line sections. For the non-homogeneous case, methods for hybrid transmission lines have been developed [23,24].

Most event localization methods determine the arrival time of TWs by processing the TWs and assigning a timestamp to each wave [5]. With the difference in timestamps, the location is determined, considering the location of the measurement devices and wave propagation characteristics. The input for the methods can be measured current or voltage phase signals [14] or phase signals transformed into modal components [25,26]. Many methods have been applied for the processing of TWs. Methods range from time-space with smoothing filter and differentiator [11], transforms in frequency space with Fourier transform and its derivatives [22], time-frequency space with derivatives of wavelet transform [27,28], use in combination with primary component analysis [29], Hilbert-Huang transform [30], to more recently proposed methods of decomposition to intrinsic mode functions [31, 32]. Additionally, most methods require information about wave propagation in the form of propagation velocity v [14], frequency-dependent velocity $v(f)$ [33,34], propagation length [35] or $\gamma(f)$ [24,36] as a set parameter for the calculation of the location. The parameters can be determined based on line modeling [32,37], using geometry, conductor properties and soil resistivity. However, it has been reported that more accurate results can be obtained by measuring the propagation characteristic of the line [17,31,38]. The measurements can be carried

out during commissioning or maintenance of the line, which usually requires the line to be de-energized. Even with measured parameters, significant errors can occur as the properties of the medium change over time due to environmental changes and the operating condition of the line [39]. In the case of overhead lines, the $\gamma(f)$ changes due to fluctuations in soil moisture and temperature [40] and in the case of underground cables, the temperature variations caused by dynamic loading lead to fluctuations of $\gamma(f)$ in the range of 2% [41,42], while on the long term $\gamma(f)$ is also influenced by insulation degradation [23].

Newer methods attempt to address the problems of obtaining propagation parameters. The online method [22] uses a signal generator to periodically generate a reference signal during the operation of the line and does not require any settings of the input parameters. The propagation function is updated based on the measurements of the reference signal. However, the application of generators to systems in operation is limited. Other methods use multiple TWs to eliminate the need for obtaining the wave propagation characteristic or parameters. One of them is based on two single-terminal devices at both ends of the line [19]. The devices assume an initial propagation velocity, which is then iteratively adjusted until the event locations from both ends match. However, the proposed method does not consider the frequency-dependence of $\gamma(f)$ and is affected by dispersion. Similarly, the methods [43,44] use two single-terminal measurements and completely eliminate the need for velocity by considering incident and reflected TWs at both ends. However, the detection of reflected waves at both ends is problematic due to the attenuation and dispersion described above.

Machine learning approaches also attempt to address the problems with changing line parameters [45,46]. However, the limiting factor in these approaches is the problem of data acquisition for training and the result only corresponds to the line segment from the training set. Methods based on simulations or model fitting have similar problems [47].

Another source of error is the inaccurate setting of the line length as an input parameter for the calculation of the absolute event location. The solution is to provide relative location in units per line length, which is then compared with a table of known feature locations on the transmission line [48]. The location of features can be determined during commissioning or maintenance by measurements or from past events where the location was determined with great accuracy. The sections between the locations are then interpolated.

Table 1 summarizes the different measurement setups for event localization. The measurement setups are grouped according to the number of devices required and how the wave propagation characteristic is considered. If the characteristic is entered as a parameter, only two TW measurements (incident and/or reflected waves) are required, but the accuracy of the method is affected by the variations in the medium. To account for the variations, three or more TW measurements are required, in which case no input parameters are needed. The table provides further requirements, assumptions and where the setups are most effective.

To account for the changes in $\gamma(f)$ and thus improve event localization, we propose a new online method that determines the frequency-dependent wave propagation characteristic from TW measurements. The main idea is to exploit the time-frequency analysis properties of the wavelet transform to simultaneously determine the frequency-dependent $\gamma(f)$ and the location of the event. Compared to existing methods that require two TW measurements and a setting for the velocity or $\gamma(f)$, the method requires three TW measurements but no settings, eliminating a major source of error. In addition, the provided frequency-dependent characteristic can be used for a better insight into the line condition. The results of the method are given relative to the monitored line length. The method can be used either in a single or double-terminal measurement setup requiring reflected waves or with three measurement devices in a multi-terminal setup requiring only incident waves, as presented in Table 1. In this paper, we focus on

Table 1

Comparison of measurement setups for event localization. Where “/” stands for a method that does not require wave propagation parameters.

Devices	Requirements				Additional assumptions	Effectiveness
	Characteristic as parameter	Reflections	Time sync	Grid topology		
1	/	2	No	Yes	Reflection is measurable and not phase shifted	Branchless topology
	v or $\gamma(f)$	1	No	Yes		
2	/	1	Yes	Yes	Consistent transmission line in 2 sections	Complex topology
	v or $\gamma(f)$	0	Yes	No		
3	/	0	Yes	No		

the three-terminal solution as we consider it the most practical due to the problems with reflected waves already discussed. Despite the need for multiple devices, the development of electronics and the solutions available on the market have significantly reduced prices compared to the past, making them more economically affordable.

The theoretical basis of the method is derived in Section 2, which is evaluated in a simulation setup described in Section 3.1. The implementation of the method is described in Section 3.2 and the results are presented and discussed in Section 4, including a comparison with other localization methods from the literature. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

2. Theory

In this section, we derive the analytical formulation of our method for localizing events and characterization of the transmission line. As mentioned above, we consider the method based on measurements of three incident TWs on a homogeneous transmission line. The setup of the measurement device with the signals and the distances considered for the analytical formulation is shown in Fig. 2.

The event location on the line is marked with the lightning bolt. The diagram shows the observed line segment with three measurement devices M_1 , M_2 and M_3 . The observed line is of length l and the three measurement devices divide it into two sections. The event is located in one section of the observed line and the other section is event free. We set the reference location position at the location of measurement device M_1 from where the event is located at distance x and the middle measurement device M_2 at distance a . The section between the measurement devices M_2 and M_3 is of length b . The length of the cable and the length between the measurement devices are not known exactly, so the method uses lengths relative to the observed line length l , which are constant.

The line can extend beyond the devices, as indicated by the dashed lines. Depending on how far the line extends beyond these two measurement devices, the time of the reflected TW and its magnitude changes. The signals at the measurement locations are denoted by s_1 to s_3 , while s_0 is the signal at the event location.

Fig. 2. Diagram of a homogeneous transmission line in 3-measurement devices setup with marked distances and considered time-series signals.

Let us first consider the well-known forward TW propagation on a transmission line [11], as shown in Fig. 1, where the waves propagate away from the event location to the measurement devices M_1 , M_2 and M_3 . From the solution of transient propagation on a transmission line [4], the relation of signals at the source location and the measurement locations in the frequency domain is:

$$\begin{aligned} S_1(f) &= e^{-x\gamma(f)} S_0(f) \\ S_2(f) &= e^{-(a-x)\gamma(f)} S_0(f) \\ S_3(f) &= e^{-(l-x)\gamma(f)} S_0(f) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where S_0 is the Fourier transform of the event signal and S_1 , S_2 and S_3 are the Fourier transforms of the signals at the location of measurement devices at distances x , $a-x$ and $l-x$ away from the event origin. Transmission line is parametrized by complex and frequency-dependent wave propagation parameter γ :

$$\gamma(f) = \alpha(f) + i\beta(f) \quad (2)$$

where α and β are frequency-dependent real and imaginary parts of γ , representing attenuation and dispersion, respectively [4].

By combining equations for S_2 and S_3 from Eq. (1) the unknown event signal can be removed from the equations:

$$\begin{aligned} S_3(f) &= e^{-(l-2x)\gamma(f)} S_1(f) \\ S_3(f) &= e^{-(l-a)\gamma(f)} S_2(f) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The measured time signals are transformed into time-frequency domain with the continuous wavelet transform (CWT) [5]. This is necessary to locate the TWs in time. The above relation in frequency domain can be written in time-frequency space with CWT [49] as:

$$\begin{aligned} W_g s_3(t, f) &= \\ &= e^{-(l-2x)(\alpha(f)+i(\beta(f)-f\beta'(f)))} W_g s_1\left(t - \frac{(l-2x)\beta'(f)}{2\pi}, f\right) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} W_g s_3(t, f) &= \\ &= e^{-(l-a)(\alpha(f)+i(\beta(f)-f\beta'(f)))} W_g s_2\left(t - \frac{(l-a)\beta'(f)}{2\pi}, f\right) \end{aligned}$$

where the transformation from Fourier transform to wavelet transform is done with the approximation of the phase parameter β with the first two terms of the Taylor series around f . $\beta'(f)$ is the first derivative of $\beta(f)$ with respect to f . W denotes the continuous wavelet transform and g denotes the mother wavelet. The equation describes that a wave at a specific frequency is delayed, attenuated and phase shifted when passing through the medium.

We can define a specific point on the measured TWs at the time of the maximum wave amplitude at each wavelet frequency, which are defined as $t_i(f)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \max(|W_g s_i(t, f)|) &= |W_g s_i(t_i(f), f)| \\ i &\in 1, 2, 3 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

If we insert the times of maximum wavelet amplitude in Eq. (4) describing the transition of wave through the line section without the event, we can express the attenuation and dispersion parts of $\gamma(f)$. As the length l is not known with enough accuracy, the attenuation

and dispersion constants are determined up to the length part. By comparing the delay, real and imaginary parts of Eq. (4), we get:

$$l\alpha(f) = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{|W_g s_2(t_2(f), f)|}{|W_g s_3(t_3(f), f)|}\right)}{1 - \frac{a}{l}} \quad (6)$$

$$l\beta'(f) = \frac{2\pi\Delta t_{32}(f)}{1 - \frac{a}{l}} \quad (7)$$

$$l\beta(f) = \frac{\angle(W_g s_2(t_2(f), f)) - \angle(W_g s_3(t_3(f), f)) + 2\pi\Delta t_{32}(f)f}{1 - \frac{a}{l}} \quad (8)$$

where the $\Delta t_{32}(f)$ is defined as follows by comparing the delay part of Eq. (4):

$$t_3(f) - t_2(f) = \Delta t_{32}(f) = \frac{l-a}{2\pi} \beta'(f) \quad (9)$$

Similarly, $\Delta t_{31}(f)$ can be defined as:

$$t_3(f) - t_1(f) = \Delta t_{31}(f) = \frac{l-2x}{2\pi} \beta'(f) \quad (10)$$

By combining the above time differences, we can express the event location:

$$\frac{x}{l} = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1 - \frac{a}{l}}{2} \frac{\Delta t_{31}(f)}{\Delta t_{32}(f)} \quad (11)$$

Event location can also be expressed by comparing amplitude or phase shift at the selected time of maximum wavelet amplitude.

The described derivation determines the attenuation and phase parameter of the wave propagation characteristic. The event location with the method in practice is frequency-dependent $\frac{x(f)}{l}$ as the timestamps at each wavelet frequency are influenced by noise, so the relative location is processed to remove outliers and averaged. The method was implemented in MatLab and evaluated with simulation, which is described in the next section.

3. Methodology

This section is divided in two subsections. Section 3.1 provides the information about the simulation setup. The results of the simulation are generated time-series signals that simulate measurements from measurement devices on a transmission line. The time-series signals were input for the proposed method, which implementation is described in Section 3.2.

3.1. Transmission line simulation

The evaluation of the proposed method was performed with the results of electromagnetic transient type simulations. The model is a modified version of the IEEE 39-bus system which specifications are provided in [50]. Compared to the base IEEE 39-bus model, the extended model provides additional information needed for the electromagnetic transient type simulations. It provides the transmission line geometry, conductor types and line lengths and also more details about loads, grid transformers and generators. But the topology of the grid is the same as the base IEEE 39-bus system.

The extended model was implemented in ATPDraw [51] and simulated with ATP-EMTP [52]. Three transmission line sections were chosen from the IEEE 39-bus system that are representative of different line lengths and conditions in the network. The chosen line sections are marked in Fig. 3, which shows a part of the IEEE 39-bus system. Chosen line sections are between buses B1-B3, B4-B8 and B5-B11.

Line lengths between the buses are of length l as marked in Fig. 2. The buses connecting two line section parts are B2, B5 and B6, which are of length a from the B1, B8 and B5 buses, respectively. On these chosen line sections, events were simulated along one part of the line to evaluate the impact of the event location x on the proposed method. The measurement devices were simulated as being located in the buses at each line section ends and the bus in-between, which connects both

Fig. 3. Part of the IEEE 39-bus system with marked line sections of different lengths and locations of measurement devices chosen for evaluation.

line parts. Both line sections have the same line parameters, so the propagation medium does not change and the line is homogeneous. The line sections on which the events for evaluation were generated lie between buses B1-B2, B5-B8 and B5-B6.

To test the method on different transmission line types, the chosen line sections were substituted with models representing underground cables. The line parameters of the simulated underground cable are gathered in Table 2. The line lengths stayed the same.

The line sections were modeled with the JMarti transmission line model [53], which models the frequency-dependent transient wave propagation on transmission lines. The universal line model [54] could also be used, but the proposed method works independently of the accuracy of the line model and the model was not fully integrated into the simulation environment used at the time of writing this paper. The parameter of the JMarti model for the ground resistivity was set to 100Ωm and the model was evaluated in the frequency range from 10Hz to 10MHz with 10 points per decade. The parameter for the steady state frequency was set to 60Hz and transposed line models were used.

Table 2
Underground cable model parameters for the frequency-dependent line model.

Parameter	Value
Cables depth below ground	2 m
Distances between cable phases	1 m
Cable core radius	28.25 mm
Cable core resistivity	$1.75 \times 10^{-8} \Omega\text{m}$
Internal insulation radius	47.5 mm
Metal shield radius	50.9 mm
Shield resistivity	$2.8 \times 10^{-7} \Omega\text{m}$
Middle insulation radius	60.0 mm
Armor radius	61.0 mm
Armor resistivity	$1.68 \times 10^{-8} \Omega\text{m}$
External insulation radius	70.0 mm
Relative insulation permittivity	2.3
Earth resistivity	100 Ωm

The simulation was performed with a time step of 10 ns adopted from a sampling frequency of 100 MHz, which is within the frequency range of 1 MHz to 1 GHz proposed by other authors [12,19]. The duration of the simulations was set to 1 ms. The voltage measurements on the buses specified in Fig. 3 were used as input for the proposed method. In practical applications, current measurements could also be used as input for the method.

In each simulation experiment, the event was generated only on one line section among the ones selected from the IEEE 39-bus model. The events were modeled on a single phase (phase C) with a current generator. The event types simulated were lightning strike and PD. The PD was modeled with double exponential function [35], while the lightning strike was modeled with Heidler’s model [8]. The event waveforms are shown in Fig. 4. The lightning strike was simulated on the overhead transmission line model and the PD event on the underground cable model.

The evaluated experiments are a combination of different event types, line lengths, event locations and transmission line types. The time-series samples from the simulated measurement devices are time synchronized and without noise. The different test experiments parameters are gathered in Table 3. To also consider more realistic conditions additional experiments were performed with different noise conditions and when the measurement devices are desynchronized. Gaussian noise was added to the raw simulation samples to evaluate the effects of noise present in the signal at the input of the method. In practice, additional filtering of the signal can be performed before input to the method. For the synchronization experiments, time delay was added to the simulation results at two measurement locations.

Fig. 4. Waveforms of the simulated event types: a) PD and b) lightning strike.

Table 3
Evaluated experiments.

Line type	Event type	Line section	Event location	Noise
Underground cable	PD	a)	$\frac{n}{10}; a; n = 1...9$	Gaussian noise
		b)	$\frac{n}{10}; a; n = 1...9$	
		c)	$\frac{n}{10}; a; n = 1...9$	
Overhead line	Lightning strike	a)	$\frac{n}{10}; a; n = 1...9$	
		b)	$\frac{n}{10}; a; n = 1...9$	
		c)	$\frac{n}{10}; a; n = 1...9$	

Fig. 5. Block diagram of the proposed method implementation.

3.2. Method implementation

The proposed method was implemented in MatLab. A block diagram of the method is presented in Fig. 5. The diagram shows the different calculation steps, labeled I. through VI., which are described below. For some steps, an instance of the results for one of the experiments are given.

The time-series samples from the simulation are input to the proposed method, which is labeled as Step I. in Fig. 5. An example of the simulation output, which was transformed with Clarke matrix to modal values after Step II., is shown in Fig. 6. In the example PD event was generated on the underground cable on the line section b) of the IEEE 39-bus system. The graph in Fig. 6 shows the alpha aerial mode of the transformed signals [26] at each measurement location for an ideal simulation without noise and with added Gaussian noise of 60 dB signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) compared to the peak value of the signal at the event location. From the graphs the incident waves as the first spikes can be observed and the reflected waves that arrive after some time. Here, the problem of reflected waves in a branched network is highlighted where it is hard to differentiate from which part of the network the reflection arrived. At the same time, the reflected waves are already quite attenuated, which is problematic in real conditions where the signal can fall below the noise, as shown in Fig. 6.

The modal samples are transformed with complex Morlet wavelet CWT [49] in Step III. The wavelet transform gives a complex time-frequency representation of the signal. The time window for the wavelet transform was 1 ms, which is the same as the simulation time. In Step IV., a local maximum in time is determined in the time-frequency space of the spectrogram representation of the transformed signal at each wavelet scale with the central frequencies f with Eq. (5). The local maximum acts also as event detection in our case, while in practice another event detection algorithm can be utilized to first identify a TW. An example of Step III. and Step IV. can be found in Fig. 7, where spectrograms for different measurement locations are shown with indicated maximum values at each wavelet scale.

Fig. 6. Modal transformed voltage signals of an ideal case (dark colors in the front) and the same case with added noise (lighter colors in the background) for line section b) with underground cable and PD event located at a distance $x = 3/10a$ after Step II.

Fig. 7. Spectrograms for line section b) with underground cable and PD event located at a distance $x = 3/10a$ after Step III. and indicated local maxima of incident waves.

In Step V., the timestamps of the local maxima are compared to determine on which side of the measurement device M_2 the event originated. This information is used to select the terminal device of the section in which no event has occurred. By comparing the timestamps of the local maximum at the selected terminal and at device M_2 , the transmission line can be characterized with the attenuation parameter and the phase parameter, while the relative location can be calculated by using all measurement locations. The values are calculated in Step VI. by Eq. (6), Eq. (8) and (11) for each wavelet central frequency, respectively.

The accuracy of the wave propagation characteristic and the relative localization of events depend on the accuracy of the timestamps at the local maxima of the wavelet transform. The event location after the calculation is not constant and depends on the wavelet central frequency at which it is evaluated. Therefore, the exact location can be determined based on the entire range of wavelet central frequencies. Here, an approximation is made so that the central frequency of each scale represents a single frequency component, as done in [49]. An example of the relative location at the wavelet central frequencies for one of the evaluated experiments is shown in Fig. 8. In this example, a very accurate result is obtained where the average relative location error is 0.05% in the frequency range between 100 kHz and 1 MHz.

Fig. 8. Measured relative location in frequency range marked with blue for an experiment on line section b) with underground cable and PD event located at a distance $x = 3/10a$ after Step VI. The average relative location between 100 kHz and 1 MHz is marked with a black line. Real event location as modeled in the simulation is marked with a red line and dashed red lines mark 0.1% error region.

We evaluated the accuracy of our method by comparing the relative localization errors. In the evaluation, we first compare the localization results in the traditional sense of relative localization accuracy in Section 4.1. In this case, we use the average relative localization at the wavelet central frequencies as the result of our method. In practice, other criteria could be used to determine the location of the event based on the frequency range of the calculated relative locations. In Section 4.2, we then evaluate the method in terms of the characterization of the line, analyzing the relative localization error in a frequency range. This is done to make the localization results easier to interpret, but the results are proportional to the characterization error.

4. Results and discussion

The proposed method was evaluated in several use cases based on the simulation setup presented in Section 3.1. First, we compared the method with the state-of-the-art event localization methods, which is presented in Section 4.1. In Section 4.2 we then evaluated the accuracy of the proposed method in more detail in different experimental setups.

4.1. Localization comparison

The proposed method was compared with localization results of the existing state-of-the-art methods focusing on methods capable of online localization. We gathered reported localization results for the existing methods and the localization results of our proposed method in Table 4. In the table, we collected the average and worst reported results from their respective papers. Different experimental setups of the transmission line were used in the papers. To make the results comparable, we present the localization results as relative error compared to the entire observed line segment and the results include only the ideal experimental cases without noise. The relative localization error is calculated with the equation:

$$x_{error} = \frac{|x_{measured} - x_{model}|}{l_{model}} \quad (12)$$

From the compared papers, the results were gathered and averaged as reported or recalculated to the same norm of the observed line length. A PD method proposed in [19] was compared to classical single- and double-terminal methods presented as the first two results in Table 4. It was tested on shorter cable section which was not a part of a network and had open terminals at the cable ends. The PD method addresses the changing line propagation parameters by using

Table 4
Comparison of localization accuracy of different event localization methods for ideal cases without noise.

Method type	Reference	Event type	Lengths evaluated [km]	Average relative accuracy [%]	Worst relative accuracy [%]	Experimental setup
Classical single-terminal	[19]	PD	1.5	7.26	9.44	Single phase cable
Classical double-terminal	[19]	PD	1.5	1.85	4.03	Single phase cable
Single-terminal with time reversal	[18]	PD	1.0 2.0	1.05 0.30	1.80 0.90	Three phase cable
Double single-terminal	[19]	PD	1.5	0.04	0.19	Single phase cable
Single-terminal with modeled characteristic	[33]	Faults	400.0	0.15	0.45	High voltage powered line
Double-terminal	[11]	Faults	117.11	0.32	0.54	High voltage powered line
Single-terminal with multiple reflections	[26]	Faults	200.0	0.03	0.16	Transmission network
Double-terminal based on modal transformation	[44]	Faults	126.0	0.04	0.16	Brazilian power grid
Multi-terminal with modeled velocity	[20]	Faults	~3.0	0.02	0.05	Middle voltage network
Proposed multi-terminal method		PD, LS	184.4	0.03	0.04	IEEE 39
			65.4	0.01	0.03	
			35.4	0.05	0.08	

single-terminal method from both line ends and iterating the result by varying the propagation velocity so that the locations of the event match from both ends. As such, it is not affected by the changing line parameters during operation and it has better localization performance compared to the classical single- and double-terminal methods, where the propagation velocity is determined from the line model. However, the method has worse performance when event is located near the line terminal where the dispersion effect on the traveling waves in both directions is not the same and with that the method accuracy is affected. Similarly, the method in [20] locates the event based on multiple measurement locations, which is extended to a branched network where the measurement locations are located at branch ends. However, only the incident waves are required and the method determines the propagation velocity based on the network section, which is not affected by the event. As the method uses the measurements from each branch end, the velocity and location result can be refined, but the frequency-dependent wave propagation characteristic is not considered. The method was evaluated on a medium voltage distribution network model.

The method presented in [33] is based on continuous wavelet transform modulus maxima, which determines the transient peak in the high frequency spectrum of the signal and is, as such, more affected by noise and has problem on longer line sections where the attenuation can reduce high frequency components beneath the noise floor level. The method is a single-terminal method and uses propagation velocity based on the transmission line model as a setting for the method. Another single-terminal method based on line modeling is proposed in [18]. The method is based on the time reversal technique, which uses simulations to determine the location of the event. The method presented in [11] is an improved double-terminal method based on measurements of line length and propagation velocity. The method presented in [26] is a single-terminal method that eliminates the need for propagation velocity and time synchronization, but requires the acquisition of additional reflections and does not consider dispersion. The method implemented in [44] also eliminates the need for line parameters and synchronization. It is based on measurements incorporating timestamps of two modal wave propagation modes. The method does not consider the frequency-dependence of wave dispersion.

For our method, we gathered the results based on the set of simulations reported in Section 3.2. Results were evaluated in the wavelet central frequency range between 100 kHz and 1 MHz. The location was evaluated at each central frequency. From the localization results in the frequency range the outliers were removed and then averaged over the frequency range for the final result. The range was chosen because

the signal at higher frequencies in a real environment is already too attenuated, especially on longer lines [22], where the traveling waves recede in the noise. While at lower frequencies, the signal wavelength is longer and the size of the sampling window for the wavelet transform has to be much larger, which is impractical in real-world applications.

Compared to other methods, our proposed method determines line propagation characteristic during operation and is, as such, not affected by medium changes similarly as [19] or [20]. Besides this, the proposed method also considers the dispersion of traveling waves as it evaluates the dispersion at each wavelet central frequency, compared to the other methods that consider the dispersion only indirectly, as in the case of [19] where bigger errors occur with events near line ends or in the case of [33] where the dispersion is evaluated at one frequency component but constant propagation velocity is considered.

To evaluate our method in more detail, we tested it in many different scenarios with a wider range of line lengths and event locations.

4.2. Method accuracy analysis

The proposed method determines the propagation characteristic of the transmission line with Eqs. (6) and (8) in a frequency range of wavelet central frequencies. At the same time, the method also calculates the event location with Eq. (11). After the calculation, the event location is not constant and depends on the wavelet central frequency at which it was evaluated. Therefore, the exact location can be evaluated based on the entire range of wavelet central frequencies, as was done in the previous section by averaging. In this section, we present the accuracy of the method under different conditions that affect the timestamps. The results are presented as localization results, which are more easily comparable with other results, while the accuracy of the propagation characteristic accuracy is proportional.

The conditions affecting the method are different event types, transmission line propagation characteristic, observed line length sections, where the sections are of different lengths and in different parts of the network, event locations along the line section, noise levels and time desynchronization between measurement devices. The simulation experiments done for the analysis are described in Section 3.2 and gathered in Table 3.

The results are presented as the distribution of frequency-dependent localization results. Where relative localization result was determined for each wavelet central frequency by equation:

$$x_{error}(f) = \frac{|x_{measured}(f) - x_{model}|}{l_{model}} \quad (13)$$

Fig. 9. Localization error distribution in the frequency range of 100 kHz to 1 MHz for line sections a), b) and c) of overhead transmission lines with lightning strike event.

and then the distribution of the results is presented in graphs where average relative localization errors and standard deviations are marked for each evaluated experiment. The frequency range of the wavelet central frequencies considered is between 100 kHz to 1 MHz. As already mentioned, higher frequency components are too attenuated in real conditions and lower frequency components require even longer sampling window for the wavelet transform, which is impractical for the implementation in a real device. The accuracy of localization is proportional to transmission line propagation characteristic accuracy.

The first set of experiments were done with lightning strike event (Fig. 4 b) with the reference overhead transmission lines model, as presented in Section 3.2. Fig. 9 shows the distribution of the relative localization errors for different transmission line segments and lightning strike event locations. The results shown include experiments in the ideal case without any noise on the transmission line and with added noise. For evaluation under noise conditions, white Gaussian noise was added to the simulation output signals at each measurement location before being processed by the proposed method. The noise added at each measurement location was set to 60 dB SNR compared to the peak amplitude value of the signal at the event location. This means the base noise level was the same for each measurement device and represents the noise floor. Consequently, the SNR at the measurement location was much worse for longer lines because the TW signal is more attenuated. To be able to compare the results for different line lengths, the results with 60 dB SNR are presented here. For the results with noise presented in Fig. 9, the simulations were evaluated with different noise seed values for 10 cases.

The second set of experiments was done with the PD event and transmission line sections replaced with the underground cable model

presented in Table 2. The distribution of the relative localization errors is shown in Fig. 10. As in the previous case, the experiments were done for different transmission line segments and event locations in ideal and noisy conditions with 60 dB SNR compared to the peak value of the event.

The results show that the proposed method works well under different conditions. The relative localization error in the frequency range of 100 kHz to 1 MHz is below 1% and mostly even below 0.1%.

In the ideal cases without noise, the measured relative localization error is mostly below 0.1%. The variations between the different line sections are because of the different grid topology around the observed line section, where the transmissions and reflections in the buses depend on the line sections and transformers connected in the buses. The results show that the event localization does not vary much between cases with different event location. The best results are in the middle of the affected line section, where the errors cancel out. When the event location is near buses, there is some variation in the localization error, as seen in experiments with lightning strike event on the line section c). While in experiments with PD event on the line section c) the apparent middle point of the line is skewed because of the transition between the cable and overhead line section.

Under noise conditions, the relative localization results are within 1%. The only outliers are the experiments with line section a) with the cable model and PD event in Fig. 10. In this case, the observed transmission line section is over 100 km long and the TW signal is so attenuated that it falls below the noise floor and the local maximum detection is not successful at the most remote measurement location (bus B3). In other cases, the results are a bit worse than the ideal cases.

Fig. 10. Localization error distribution in the frequency range of 100 kHz to 1 MHz for line sections a), b) and c) of underground cable with PD event.

Fig. 11. Localization error distribution in the frequency range of 100kHz to 1 MHz for underground cable in section c) with PD event, when the measurement devices are desynchronized. 100 ns, 200 ns and 400 ns time mismatch is applied to two of the measurement devices. Measurement device indicated with '+' is ahead of the reference time and the device with '-' behind the reference time.

From the results, it is shown that the chosen sampling frequency and frequency range are sufficient, but it can be adapted for specific event types, since the slower changing transient events contain less energy at higher frequencies and vice versa. The attenuation and noise limit the high frequency range. The lower frequency limit is set by the wavelet resolution, as it is limited by the sampling time window and the sampling frequency, as well as the energy of the transient signals in the lower frequency range.

The measurement devices in the proposed method must be synchronized in time if more than one measurement device is used. To evaluate the performance of the method under different synchronization conditions, a constant time delay was applied to two of the three measurement devices. One device can always be set as a reference, as its time error can be added to the other two. The worst performance is expected when the two devices have the opposite time error, i.e. one is ahead and the other is behind the reference device. The results of event localization, when different combinations of devices are desynchronized, are shown in Fig. 11. The experiments presented refer to the PD event on the underground cable in line section c). This represents one of the worst conditions, as the line is relatively short and the timing error has the greatest influence. Two devices were assigned a constant timing error of 100 ns, 200 ns and 400 ns. One device was ahead and the other was behind the timing of the third device, which had an absolute timing.

In the evaluated experiments, the relative localization error is well below 1%, even with a time deviation of 400 ns on two devices. The synchronization accuracy can be achieved with modern systems, e.g. with the GPS. The synchronization of the device clock achievable with GPS is typically below 100 ns relative to absolute time [15,55]. The jitter of the sampling time that occurs in the event duration is small enough to be considered negligible. Modern devices can maintain good timing accuracy even when GPS is not available [56].

One of the specific parameters affecting our method is the location of the measurement device M_2 in a three-device setup. From the presented results, it is shown that it does not significantly affect the localization and characterization results. In practice larger distance b between the measurement devices reduces the noise error on the CWT timesteps as the time difference is larger.

An implementation of a measurement device requires a sampling frequency of 10 MHz to 100 MHz with support for time synchronization to GPS or synchronization via an optical cable. The input must be compatible with a sensor for voltage or current measurements. Filtering and noise reduction can be performed in the initial signal processing steps to improve signal quality. The real-time processing capabilities for CWT can be implemented in the measurement devices and only the detected local maximum timestamps can be sent to a central location

where the rest of the proposed method is implemented. Real-time processing of CWT requires advanced computational resources, but there have been recent advances in implementation, as presented in [57]. The most suitable implementation is with a Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA), as in [58]. Optimizations of the required frequency range and time window should be considered for the problem at hand. The detection of the local maximum could also be optimized by reducing the number of central wavelet frequencies. Another option is to deploy other event detection algorithm on the device itself and then transmit a measurement window containing the detected event to a central location where all steps of the proposed method are implemented. This implementation reduces the computational requirements of the measurement devices.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we propose a new online method for localizing events on transmission lines. The method analyzes the traveling wave in the time-frequency domain of the wavelet transform. Based on three traveling wave measurements, the propagation medium is characterized and the origin of the event is localized. The method thus solves the problem of having to know the wave propagation characteristic of the transmission line in advance. This eliminates the setting as an input parameter for the algorithm, which is one of the limitations of existing methods, because the characteristic of the propagation medium changes over time during the operation of the line. At the same time, the characteristic of the transmission line is evaluated in a frequency domain, which improves the localization process by considering the dispersion effect.

We have compared the proposed method with other TW methods for event localization, where our method is on par with the best reported methods and has the advantage of accounting for the changing transmission medium over time. We performed a comprehensive analysis of the capabilities of our method in a simulation environment. The method was tested under various conditions in an IEEE 39-bus system model, taking into account different locations in the grid, line lengths, line characteristic, event types, event locations and noise. The results show that the relative localization error is below 0.1% in most cases. The specifics of our proposed method in terms of synchronization requirements were also evaluated. Synchronization has the greatest impact on the accuracy of the method for shorter line sections.

Future work will focus on integrating the proposed method into a test measurement setup and later developing a stand-alone device and the supporting system. In addition, we will investigate where the online transmission line characterization data can be utilized for new services besides improving event localization.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Marko Hudomalj: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Andrej Trost:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Andrej Čampa:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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